

Optically Active Ketimines from D(+)-2-Oxo-10-Bornanesulphonic Acid

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Optically active D(-)-2-Arylimino-10-Camphanesulphonic acids have been prepared by dehydration of D(+) Camphor-10-sulphonates of different bases as well as by heating bases with D(+)-Camphor-10-sulphonic acid. The second method is one step, convenient, and yields of the products are comparatively very good. Their optical rotations have been taken in different solvents. The specific rotations are maximum when aryl group is *p*-anisyl and minimum when it is *o*-nitrophenyl.

Shriner and coworker¹ prepared optically active 2-phenylimino-10-camphanesulphonic acid by the dehydration of aniline-D(+)-Camphor-10-sulphonate. In order to study optical activity, we have prepared some more optically active 2-Arylimino 10-Camphanesulphonic acids of the type (I) by the dehydration of D (+) Camphor-10-sulphonates of different bases, where R=phenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chlorophenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl, 2, 5-dichlorophenyl, *p*-bromophenyl, *o*- and *p*-anisyl, *p*-acetylamino-phenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenyl etc. We have

also prepared the same compounds by heating D (+)-Camphor-10-sulphonic acids with different bases at 160°-200° for 2 to 3 hrs. The products obtained by both the methods are identical. The second method is one step, convenient and the yield of the products are comparatively good. The optical rotations have been taken in different solvents (Tables 1 and 2). The specific rotations are maximum ($[\alpha]_D^{25} = -225$ l, 1; c, 1; acetic acid) when R= *p*-anisyl and minimum ($[\alpha]_D^{25} = -25$ l, 1; C, 0.2 acetic acid) when it is *o*-nitrophenyl. The specific

TABLE 1—OPTICALLY ACTIVE 2-ARYLIMINO-10-CAMPHANESULPHONIC ACID OF TYPE (I)

Sr. No.	R=Aryl	Mol. Formula	% yield		m.p. °C	% of N		Acetic acid $[\alpha]_D^{25}$; 1, 1
			Method A	Method B		Found	Calc.	
1	Phenyl	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ NS	87	97	287-88	4.50	4.56	-190.0
2	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₂ NS	93	76	262-63	4.30	4.36	-150.0
3	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₂ NS	78	84	225-26	4.37	4.36	-142.2
4	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₂ NS	75	70	—	4.28	4.36	-172.8
5	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ NSCl	81	89	246-47	4.00	4.10	-109.5
6	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ NSCl	98	95	—	4.12	4.10	-109.1
7	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ NSCl	95	94	262-63	4.07	4.10	-174.1
8	2, 5-Dichlorophenyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₂ NSCl ₂	88	93	272-73	3.70	3.72	-57.1
9	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ NSBr	87	87	243-44	3.58	3.62	-103.5
10	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₃ NS	94	94	272-73	4.20	4.15	-150.0
11	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₃ NS	98	93	270-71	4.18	4.15	-225.0
12	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	94	95	203-5	8.00	7.95	-25.0
13	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	92	87	251-52	7.85	7.95	-78.9
14	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	94	97	261-62	7.72	7.95	-161.5
15	<i>p</i> -Acylaminophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₂ S	89	93	308-10	7.70	7.69	-180.0
16	Benzyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₂ NS	90	96	242-43	4.34	4.36	-121.3

N. B. All compounds gave correct C, H, analysis.

TABLE 2—SPECIFIC ROTATIONS OF OPTICALLY ACTIVE 2-ARYLIMINO-10-CAMPHANE SULPHONIC ACID IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS AT ROOM TEMP.

Sr. No.	R=Aryl	Chloroform l, l	Methanol l, l	Ethanol l, l	Pyridine l, l
1	Phenyl	-170.0	-165.0	-150.0	+10.0
2	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	-128.0	-140.0	-135.0	+51.5
3	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	-127.8	-129.8	-125.0	+4.5
4	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	-155.0	-163.6	-157.9	-25.0
5	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	-90.0	-95.0	-77.7	+64.8
6	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	-100.0	-102.1	-84.22	+40.0
7	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	-105.5	-159.6	—	+60.0
8	2, 5-Dichlorophenyl	-81.3	-30.8	—	+43.8
9	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	-95.6	-107.6	—	+39.0
10	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	-100.0	-118.5	—	-35.0
11	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	-205.0	-200.0	—	-55.6
12	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	—	—	—	-62.5
13	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	—	-18.2	—	+31.3
14	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	—	+13.6	—	+62.5
15	<i>p</i> -Acylaminophenyl	—	—	—	—
16	Benzyl	-105.0	-102.0	-90.0	-114.2

rotation of *p*-isomers are more than *o*- and *m*-isomers. They are unstable in solution and even in presence of moisture as they undergo mutarotation¹.

Experimental :

(a) *Preparation of D(+)-Camphor-10-sulphonates of different bases :*

D(+)-Camphor-10-sulphonates were prepared by condensing equivalent amount of D(-)-Camphor-10-sulphonic acid with different bases in ethyl acetate or absolute ethanol¹⁻⁵.

(b) *Preparation of 2-arylimino-10-camphanesulphonic acids :*

(i) *Method A :* Dehydration of D(+)-Camphor-10-sulphonates (a) :

D(+)-Camphor-10-sulphonate of a base (0.01 mole) was heated at 160°-200° for 2 to 3 hrs. The product obtained was crystallised from chloroform and petroleum ether. A semi solid product was obtained when *p*-toluidine and *m*-chloroaniline-D(+)-Camphor-10-sulphonates were heated. The dehydration of aniline, benzylamine and *p*-aminoacetanilide salt was carried out by Shriner but the m.p. were

taken on mequenne bloc. The physical constants are recorded in Table 1. The optical rotations were taken in different solvents (Table 2). The neutral equivalents of all products were determined which gave correct value of molecular weights.

(ii) *Method B :*

A mixture of D(+)-Camphor-10-sulphonic acid (0.01 mole) and a base (0.01 mole) was heated in an oil bath at 160°-200° for 3 hrs. The product obtained was crystallised from chloroform and petroleum ether. The products obtained by both the methods (A and B) are identical (Table 1 and 2).

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